

**Projection spread caused by missingness
in PCA on modern West Eurasian populations:
Approx. # non-missing SNPs = 18000**

**True position of individual
(Individual : Population)**

- HGDP00666 : Sardinian
- △ HGDP00879 : Russian
- + HGDP00607 : BedouinB
- × TP08 : Sicilian
- ◇ abh27 : Abkhasian
- ▽ NA13597 : Atayal
- ⊠ ADR00514 : Nganasan
- * ALT-116 : Tubalar
- ⊠ HGDP00213 : Pathan
- ⊠ Loschbour_published.DG : WHG

Approx Geographical location a Caucasus a Middle_East a North_Asia a North_Europe a SouthEur a Uralic